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THE NETWORK OF ACADEMIC COIN COLLECTIONS (NUMID)

University Numismatic Collections in European Academic History

Research and teaching collections shape the identity of universities across all fields of knowledge: from A for archaeology to Z for zoology, Europe boasts a rich and diverse landscape of academic collections.¹ Most are housed within research institutes or libraries, while others are attached to university heritage services, integrated into research clusters, or displayed in university museums. These collections represent a fascinating dimension of the history of science. Over the centuries, ever richer holdings of documents, artifacts, and specimens have been acquired, preserved, classified, restored, and catalogued – and, above all, studied and integrated into teaching. Like libraries and archives, university collections have, since their inception, fulfilled an essential role in academia as research infrastructures and memory institutions. They have constituted – and continue to constitute – arenas for critical engagement with the material remains of human cultures. They dynamically organize bodies of knowledge while providing a framework for developing and testing research theories and practices. As incubators of scholarly culture, object collections embody a constellation of values, practices, and research tools. This constellation is sustained by a plurality of actors with varied social and academic roles, organized in networks and driven by their own interests, approaches, and methods.

Within this vast and diverse universe, one particular type of collection shines with a distinctive lustre – at once symbolic and material: university coin collections.² From the 17th century onward, the first academic numismatic collections took shape in many institutions, often originating from professors' private holdings, princely donations, secularized church property, or hoard finds. They count among the oldest collections of tangible cultural objects preserved at universities. Coins captured the attention of scholars at an early stage because of their status as authentic witnesses to past eras, situated at the crossroads of politics, economy, and society. Through their technical features, iconography, inscriptions, and contexts of production and discovery, coins offer valuable insights into forms of human interaction, strategies of legitimating power, and the dynamics of economic systems. Whether through their materials, design elements (including mint marks), traces of use or later alterations, or modes of circulation and transmission, coins allow for a nuanced reading of historical contexts often difficult to reconstruct from written sources alone.

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¹ Weber 2010.

² Martin, Mulsow & Wienand 2025.

With the rise of the modern sciences, awareness of the specific heuristic value of coins as a distinct category of historical evidence gradually established itself – first within the universalist scholarly cultures of the early modern period, and later within the historical, archaeological, and philological disciplines that emerged from them. Interest in coins as historical sources has been, and remains, especially strong in disciplines that study monetized cultures but possess only fragmentary literary or administrative documentation: in particular the study of Antiquity (notably Greek and Roman history and classical archaeology), Byzantine studies, and medieval studies. In the field of Oriental studies, Islamic coins drew particular attention because of their distinctive status as miniaturized media of writing: the absence of figurative iconography left more space for inscriptions, sometimes sufficiently rich to reflect entire hierarchies of power.³ In these disciplines, university coin collections also played a key role in the emergence of the principle of autopsy – direct first-hand examination. Working directly with objects, in both research and teaching, helped sharpen awareness of the scholarly potential inherent in immediate encounters with material sources. In turn, this also influenced the methodological approaches applied to other kinds of material documents, such as inscriptions, papyri, or sculpture.⁴

Metallic composition, contexts of minting and discovery, as well as factors pertaining to the individual histories of objects – such as later interventions; state of preservation; conservation treatments; provenance; or their contextualization within a collection – open avenues of analysis that extend far beyond traditional antiquarian or art-historical approaches. These data are of value to a wide range of disciplines in the humanities and social sciences: from economic anthropology and the study of money and power to the analysis of political discourse and monarchy, social and cultural history, the history of mentalities, religious studies, and the history of collections. Far from a marginal phenomenon, academic numismatics is firmly embedded in its disciplinary contexts: the histories of both Classical and Oriental studies would be incomplete without the history of their collections. Work on these holdings has been crucial for the development of numismatic classification systems, documentation strategies, research approaches, and pedagogical models. The increasing interconnection of university collections with archaeological services and extra-university museums has likewise enriched methodological approaches in numismatics.

By their very nature, numismatic objects remain especially well-suited for university teaching in the humanities even today. Coin collections provide direct access to a category of historical sources that is both eloquent and readily usable in academic instruction. These original objects, compact and

³ Heidemann 2000.

⁴ Lehmann 2025.

relatively durable, can be examined firsthand in seminars. Their iconography and inscriptions, standardized yet rich in variation, enable the systematic recording of technical data, the description of visual and textual programs, the consultation of bibliographic references, and the historical contextualization of each piece. Students in historical and archaeological disciplines show a strong interest in working with such original sources. In practical seminars, exhibition projects, or research assignments, they can explore new approaches, test methods, and formulate novel questions. Direct engagement with the objects fosters the development of both disciplinary expertise and transferable skills – and in some cases, even inspires thesis projects.

Academic numismatics can realize its full potential, in both research and teaching, only through close engagement with coin collections. Across the relevant disciplines, a wide range of academic actors – from students and doctoral candidates to research assistants, faculty, and professors – have, in one way or another, incorporated coin collections into their scholarly, pedagogical, or administrative work. From the rise of the modern sciences in the 16th and 17th centuries to the present, such engagements have stimulated reflection on academic identity, shaped conceptions of research, and influenced the role of academic institutions – even as the structures, functions, and dynamics of collection-based work have undergone profound transformations over time.

This transformation is evident in the shift whereby most university numismatic collections, once commonly attached to university libraries in the early modern period (16th–18th centuries), were, with the growing disciplinary specialization of the 19th and 20th centuries, increasingly integrated into research institutes. Today, university coin collections are divided roughly equally between institutes of archaeology and ancient history (Greek and Roman history) and, more rarely, departments of Oriental studies, theology, philology, or Byzantine studies. Only a few remain in university libraries. Some are administered by university heritage services; in a small number of cases, they are integrated into university museums, which provide curatorial care and public presentation.

Overall, university numismatic collections in Europe today preserve a unique heritage of major scholarly and cultural significance, estimated at around one million objects.⁵ For comparison, the Fitzwilliam Museum in Cambridge, with some 60,000 ancient coins, already ranks among the ten global ‘core collections’ of ancient numismatics. The majority of university

⁵ It is not yet possible to arrive at a definitive quantification of all university numismatic collections in Europe. For the German-speaking area, university collections are estimated to comprise between 350,000 and 400,000 objects (see Wienand 2025, p. 26–27). The two collections at the Universities of Oxford and Cambridge alone already comprise nearly half a million items.

holdings consist of coins from Greek and Roman Antiquity, while another substantial component consists of Islamic coins. Smaller, though still notable, groups include Byzantine, Persian, Jewish, Indo-Bactrian, Chinese, and Celtic coins. Alongside coins in the strict sense, the collections also encompass medallions and medals, tesseræ, imitations and other pseudo-monetary objects, as well as related items such as ingots, seals, and tokens – and, in certain cases, items of the ancient minor arts. Coins from the European Middle Ages and the modern era – common in many museum collections – make up only a minor portion of university holdings, except in a few cases where they are more prominent. The same applies to modern medals and banknotes.

With the increasing specialization of disciplines in Classical studies, interest in systematically enriching coin collections grew markedly. In this context, large numbers of coin reproductions entered collections – including plaster casts, galvanoplastic replicas, electrotypes, and sulfur casts. At times, ancient or modern forgeries were deliberately acquired to fill gaps.⁶ Many university collections also incorporated coins from isolated finds or hoards, whether through official allocations of individual specimens or entire hoards, or through donations from finders under find-sharing agreements. Collections were further expanded through exchanges – notably between university collections or with museum coin cabinets – and, on several occasions, by acquisitions from major museum holdings through the de-accession of duplicates.⁷ In some research institutes, collections were augmented, more or less systematically, with reference examples of current issues from state mints. Around these composite ensembles – combining original objects and reproductions – specialized infrastructures gradually developed: numismatic libraries, archival resources and research card files, slide collections, and, more recently, digital research platforms.

Ultimately, each university coin collection has its own character and history. In some cases, distinctly specialized holdings emerged: at Jena and Tübingen, significant research collections in Islamic numismatics; at the BIBLE+ORIENT Museum in Fribourg, a collection focused on coins of the ancient Levant; and at Basel, Düsseldorf, and Frankfurt am Main, systematically organized collections of plaster coin casts for research purposes.⁸ The Numismatic Institute in Vienna (Institut für Numismatik und Geldgeschichte) developed the Numismatische Zentralkartei, an extensive index file that serves as an important reference tool for numismatic research. The possibilities for developing these holdings and their associated infrastructures depend on the human and financial resources available at each

⁶ Stoess, Weisser & Baltz 2024.

⁷ For instance in Strasbourg: Wirbelauer 2025.

⁸ Other holdings preserved in certain university collections also stem from research travels undertaken by specialists in Classical or Oriental studies, or from religious missions – as in Basel or Greifswald.

site – two factors that remain scarce due to the chronic underfunding of research infrastructures in the humanities, especially in smaller disciplines such as numismatics. Coherent collection management policies – like those observed in museums, which allow continuous work on the holdings independent of staff turnover – have existed only sporadically at a few universities. In general, no fixed budgets are allocated to the systematic expansion of collections. Their development has often been driven by specific research interests, but also by other factors – sometimes scholarly, sometimes contingent, and often simply by chance.

Most university coin collections today comprise only a few thousand original coins. Some, however, hold far larger – indeed remarkable – numbers of objects, as illustrated by two cases in the United Kingdom: the Ashmolean Museum (University of Oxford) houses around 300,000 numismatic objects, and the Fitzwilliam Museum (University of Cambridge) nearly 200,000. In Germany, the two largest university collections are those of the University Library of Leipzig and the Tübingen Research Unit for Islamic Numismatics (Forschungsstelle für Islamische Numismatik Tübingen, FINI), each with around 90,000 coins.⁹ Austria's largest academic numismatic collection is held by the Institute of Numismatics and Monetary History (Institut für Numismatik und Geldgeschichte) at the University of Vienna, with about 30,000 coins.¹⁰ Switzerland, by contrast, was the cradle of one of the world's oldest academic coin collections but today no longer possesses substantial holdings of this kind: founded in 1661 at the University of Basel, the once most eminent university coin collection of Switzerland is now preserved in the city's Historical Museum.¹¹

An International Network of University Numismatic Collections

Each collection is unique, yet together they form – through their shared grounding in the scholarly culture of numismatics – a coherent constellation of scholarly networks and research practices, organized around a decentralized corpus of numismatic objects. From the perspective of the history of science, the significance of university coin collections can be fully appreciated only by considering this remarkable configuration in its international dimension. Moreover, the experience of the past two decades has made it increasingly clear that these collections benefit greatly from scholarly exchange, collaborative research, and mutual support – particularly when facing challenges of staffing, budgetary constraints, or administrative demands.

To fully realize this potential, numerous university coin collections have joined together in the Network of Academic Coin Collections (NUMiD), an

⁹ Mackert & Uhlmann 2025; Hanstein 2025.

¹⁰ Baer & Emmerig 2025.

¹¹ Wienand 2025, pp. 23–24.

international network dedicated to numismatic research and digitization.¹² Established with support from the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung, BMBF) between 2017 and 2021,¹³ the initiative originated in Germany but today extends across seven countries: Austria, France, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Switzerland, and Ukraine (see the map of participating universities in Figure 1).

Fig. 1 – Map of the sites of the Network of Academic Coin Collections (NUMiD) and of the members of the ikmk.net network. Created by Anna Haake

Operating under the patronage of the International Numismatic Council, the member collections constitute a network of scholarly mutual support. Membership entails no fees or formal obligations but rests on the voluntary commitment of its participants. Institutions exchange information on numismatic projects and developments and, to the extent of their means, share expertise and provide assistance at both scholarly and administrative levels.

Beyond this collaborative dimension, the Network of Academic Coin Collections also enables its members to adopt a common digitization strategy. In this context, the network works closely with the Berlin Coin Cabinet (Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen zu Berlin), which plays a pioneering global

¹² Wienand 2017; Dahmen *et al.* 2018.

¹³ Kemmers *et al.* 2021.

role in the digitization of coin collections.¹⁴ This partnership allows university members to benefit from dedicated instances within an interconnected database system, developed largely by the Berlin Coin Cabinet. Each participating university receives its own digital coin cabinet, while the federated portal numid.online, which serves as a shared digital catalog, provides global access to all digitized data from the participating collections. In collaboration with several public numismatic collections – notably the Berlin Coin Cabinet, the Department of Coins and Medals at the Kunsthistorisches Museum in Vienna, and the Coin Cabinet Winterthur – data from the university databases are also integrated into the international portal ikmk.net (the institutions in this broader network are likewise shown on the map in Figure 1).¹⁵

The digitization system is specifically designed for the needs of numismatic research. Unlike generic image databases used by many museums and universities for collection inventories, the system developed by the Berlin Coin Cabinet is tailored to the requirements of detailed documentation and scholarly publication of numismatic objects. It also provides interfaces for interconnection with numismatic research portals, which are currently expanding rapidly – such as those established by the American Numismatic Society, the University of Oxford, or the Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences.¹⁶ Beyond these specialized platforms, which are gaining increasing importance for the field, the data can also be transmitted to broader cultural heritage databases, such as europeana.eu.

The database model developed in Berlin allows curators to structure and enrich data, providing portal users with a wide range of search functions – including an interactive map for visualizing mints and find spots – and presenting results in a clear, accessible, and visually polished manner. Each record includes high-quality photographs of both sides of the object, technical and descriptive data, and relevant bibliographic references (see the screenshot in Figure 2).

¹⁴ Weisser 2020; Weisser & Wienand 2025.

¹⁵ Dahmen *et al.* 2012; Weisser, Dahmen *et al.* 2025. In addition to the members of the NUMID network, the following institutions are also part of the IKMK network: Athens, KIKPE Foundation; Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen zu Berlin; Brunswick, Herzog Anton Ulrich-Museum; Cologne, Römisch-Germanisches Museum; Hamburg, Hamburger Kunsthalle; Mainz, Bischöfliches Dom- und Diözesanmuseum; Münster, LWL-Museum für Kunst und Kultur; Salzburg, Salzburg Museum; Vienna, Münzkabinett des Kunsthistorischen Museums; Winterthur, Münzkabinett Winterthur; Wolfenbüttel, Museum Wolfenbüttel.

¹⁶ See, for example: numismatics.org/pella (Coinage of the Macedonian Kings of the Argead Dynasty), numismatics.org/sco (Seleucid Coins Online), numismatics.org/pco (Ptolemaic Coins Online), numismatics.org/crro (Coinage of the Roman Republic Online), numismatics.org/ocre (Online Coins of the Roman Empire), rpc.ashmus.ox.ac.uk (Roman Provincial Coinage Online), or corpus-nummorum.eu (Thrace, Mysia, Troad, and Moesia).

HOME SEARCH MAP

« < 1 2 3 4 5 > »

Könige von Lydien: Kroisos
(Turkey, Lydia)
Stater, 561-546 v. Chr.
17821
WÜ (Uni, MWM) Ka 1737 = H
6290

Persis: Großkönig
Dareikos, 5. Jh. v. Chr.
24272
ER (Uni, Antikenslg.) H 197

Persis
Dareikos, 5. Jh. v. Chr.
43075
MZ (Uni, Alte Gesch.) 33

Elis
Elis (Greece, Elis)
Trihemionbol, ca. 365-
363 v. Chr.
26472
ER-N (UB) WG 246

Pumiathon
Kition (Larnaka) (Cyprus,
Cypros)
1/2 Stater (Hemistater), 361-
312 v. Chr.
49216
TÜ (Uni, Klass. Arch.) SNG
Tübingen 4581

Zeugitana: Karthago
Karthago (Tunisia,
Zeugitana)
Stater, 350-320 v. Chr.
17543
WÜ (Uni, MWM) Ka 1132 = H
6498

*Fig. 2: The shared numid.online portal of the
Network of Academic Coin Collections. Screenshot*

The system also permits documentation and management of internal information not published in the digital cabinets – such as physical location details, staff notes, or loan information. Each digitized object is assigned a permalink, and the data are also provided in machine-readable form via JSON and LIDO interfaces. Through the collective online catalogs numid.online and ikmk.net, the holdings of partner institutions can be searched jointly. With more than 150,000 records from over 45 collections across several European countries, the network today stands as a major actor on the international stage.¹⁷ Within the IKMK network, nearly one-third of the digitized objects currently come from partner university collections. The Berlin system is also employed in projects on coin finds, including inventories from Priene and Pergamon (Turkey), Tall Zira'a (Jordan), and Olympia (Greece).¹⁸

¹⁷ An up-to-date overview of the participating collections is available at ikmk.net/collection_search.

¹⁸ See ikmk.smb.museum/mk_priene (B. Weisser), ikmk.smb.museum/mk_pergamon (J. Chameroy), muenzen.tallziraa.de (K. Dahmen). A portal is currently being developed for the site of Olympia (S. Killen), with further excavation sites (Assos, Patara) to follow.

The cornerstone of this technical infrastructure is centralized data standardization, which allows the network to draw collectively on a common authority file developed and continuously enriched by the Berlin Coin Cabinet. Established with rigorous scholarly standards, this corpus of authority data is essential for ensuring consistent, high-quality metadata across the network. Thanks to this common basis, digitized records can be searched jointly across institutional boundaries and exported via unified interfaces. The standardized concepts are semantically enriched by links to external scholarly vocabularies – for example, to the Virtual International Authority File (viaf.org) for persons (monetary authorities, depicted figures), to geonames.org for geographic data (mint and find locations), and to nomisma.org for numismatics-specific concepts (denominations, materials, etc.). These links are integrated into the digitized records and exported with them, thereby linking each object description to multiple external scholarly resources and making it a genuine node in the Semantic Web. All standardized concepts managed by the Berlin Coin Cabinet can be consulted via its authority data portal (Normdatenportal), accessible at ikmk.smb.museum/ndp.¹⁹ The corresponding vocabularies – currently over 22,000 numismatic concepts, including more than 15,000 entries for persons and legal entities, over 4,000 places, and more than 2,500 coin denominations – have become a major reference resource in numismatics.

Whereas a decade ago a wide variety of approaches to digitizing numismatic collections still prevailed in museums and universities, cooperation between university collections and the Berlin Coin Cabinet has since emerged as a reference model. Today it stands as an exemplary paradigm for collection digitization specifically adapted to numismatic material, closely integrated with research, and conceived on an inter-institutional scale. Within this international network, university and museum collections pool resources and provide open access – in accordance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) – to high-quality, machine-readable images and metadata for their holdings.

In collaboration with the Berlin Coin Cabinet, the network also seeks to minimize the burdens that collective digitization might place on its members. The Coin Cabinet has provided partner institutions with free licenses for its database and standardized thesauri. In many cases, project funding has made it possible to cover the costs of local database installations. Cooperation agreements further stipulate that any functional developments of the system – regardless of which partner initiates or finances them – benefit the network as a whole. This arrangement reduces maintenance costs for individual partners. In addition, partner institutions provide each other with support in the form of advice and training, offered on a collegial and voluntary basis. Specialized equipment for coin photography is made

¹⁹ Dahmen 2022.

available free of charge, and financial support has at times been provided for student assistants.

By licensing a database system designed specifically for the needs of digital numismatics, administered centrally on the technical side and complemented by a shared quality assurance framework, all members of the network benefit from continuous software updates and sustained support from a major institutional partner – an essential factor, particularly for collections with limited staff and resources, in a constantly evolving digital environment. Universities thus fully profit from the partnership with the Berlin Coin Cabinet in developing, implementing, and sustainably operating an interoperable multi-institutional research data infrastructure, as well as in managing the scholarly data it generates. In this role, the Berlin Coin Cabinet functions as a research-oriented data curator with a long-term perspective, assuming key responsibilities for maintaining scholarly standards in numismatics regardless of staff fluctuations within partner institutions. Today the Berlin Coin Cabinet stands among the world's most active public institutions in numismatic research and has become a key driver of the discipline's digitization.²⁰

Through close cooperation between academic and museum partners, the network seeks to strengthen numismatics as a core discipline of history and archaeology while underscoring its central role in the preservation of cultural heritage. Yet the concrete work has always been – and continues to be – carried out locally, within the collections themselves. The extent to which a university collection can benefit from the support offered depends directly on its capacity to engage in foundational work on the objects. No collection is obliged to the network: NUMiD does not impose directives but offers perspectives, establishes structural foundations for coordinated digitization geared toward basic research, and provides support. With the digitization system developed in Berlin, university collections now have a tool that enables them to focus fully on core scholarly tasks. What remains indispensable, however, are the fundamental skills of numismatic research at the local level: a trained eye, the ability to produce precise and rigorous descriptions, and the readiness to engage critically and in depth with the state of research.

The involvement of students in hands-on work with collections should not be underestimated: it provides a structured pathway into numismatics and plays a central role in training and renewing future generations of scholars. Intensive use of the Berlin database system at universities has on several occasions prompted the development of functions specifically tailored to the needs of higher education. Under the heading eNumis, for example, a feature was introduced that enables students in numismatics courses, under supervision, to contribute to the digitization of collections: working

²⁰ Weisser & Wienand 2025.

directly with original objects, they create records step by step for their institution's digital cabinet. These records can then be published and remain available online as validated scholarly documentation. For students, this process is doubly motivating: they work directly with historical objects, and the results of their efforts do not remain unused but instead enrich scholarly documentation as openly accessible digital resources.²¹

The system has also been expanded with an eMuseum module, which enables the straightforward design of online numismatic exhibitions directly linked to the records of objects in the digital cabinets.²² This feature is of particular value for teaching, as it not only supports the precise identification of objects but also fosters their thematic contextualization. Here again, the publication of results serves as a strong motivational factor for students and yields clear pedagogical benefits. The new functionalities open a wide spectrum of opportunities for engaging with collections: 3D models, videos, and podcasts can likewise be integrated. The fact that student projects created in the course of teaching are published and remain reusable both motivates students and makes them aware of the possibilities opened by digitization, while at the same time sensitizing them to the standards of rigorous scholarly practice. With the active involvement of students, roughly 50,000 objects have already been made available online through the network's university portal, and multiple online numismatic exhibitions have been created in recent years.²³ This growing corpus of data, knowledge, and expertise testifies not only to the cultural heritage of two and a half millennia of monetized culture but also to the considerable potential that university collections hold for research and teaching in the digital age.

* * *

Digitization has added a new and stimulating dimension to the scholarly activity of university numismatic collections. Early attempts by some institutions to document their holdings with in-house software and make them available online have now given way to a coordinated and collective approach. This shift is partly explained by the fact that university institutes rarely possess the human and financial resources required to develop and maintain long-term, web-based database systems. More fundamentally, however, it reflects a crucial realization: only very large, homogeneously structured datasets can provide the foundation for genuinely new scholarship. Under this condition, large-scale statistical analyses, big-data processing, and applications of artificial intelligence can produce results of a scope and depth unattainable without digital tools. From the earliest stages of digitally oriented research networks in numismatics, university collec-

²¹ Stricker, Weber & Wienand 2021.

²² Wienand 2018.

²³ An overview is available on the page ikmk.net/eMuseum.

tions have played an active role in this dynamic. The benefits of this collective effort extend far beyond the mere publication of object records. For the first time in the history of university numismatic collections, a shared and sustainable knowledge base is taking shape – at the intersection of research, teaching, and scholarly communication – within the framework of an unprecedented international collaboration.

Member Institutions of the Network of Academic Coin Collections (NUMiD) (as of September 2025)

Austria

Vienna: Universität Wien, Institut für Numismatik und Geldgeschichte

Graz: Universität Graz, Institut für Alte Geschichte und Altertumskunde

France

Strasbourg: Institut d'Histoire Grecque et Romaine, Faculté des Sciences Historiques, Université de Strasbourg

Germany

Augsburg: Universität Augsburg, Alte Geschichte

Berlin: Freie Universität Berlin, Alte Geschichte

Berlin: Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Kunstsammlung

Bochum: Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Historisches Institut

Bonn: Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität Bonn, Akademisches Kunstmuseum/Antikensammlung

Braunschweig: Technische Universität Braunschweig, Alte Geschichte

Cologne: Universität zu Köln, Historisches Institut, Alte Geschichte

Cologne: Universität zu Köln, Institut für Altertumskunde, Byzantinistik

Cologne: Universität zu Köln, Institut für Altertumskunde, Klassische Philologie

Constance: Universität Konstanz, Universitätsbibliothek

Düsseldorf: Heinrich-Heine-Universität Düsseldorf, Alte Geschichte

Eichstätt: Katholische Universität Eichstätt-Ingolstadt, Alte Geschichte

Erlangen: Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Antikensammlung

Erlangen: Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Universitätsbibliothek

Frankfurt am Main: Goethe-Universität, Institut für Archäologische Wissenschaften Abt. I (Klassische Archäologie)

Frankfurt am Main: Goethe-Universität, Institut für Archäologische Wissenschaften II (Archäologie von Münze, Geld und Wirtschaft in der Antike)

Freiberg: Technische Universität Bergakademie Freiberg, Universitätsbibliothek

- Freiburg im Breisgau: Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, Alte Geschichte
- Freiburg im Breisgau: Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, Christliche Archäologie und Byzantinische Kunstgeschichte
- Gießen: Justus-Liebig-Universität Gießen, Antikensammlung
- Göttingen: Georg-August-Universität Göttingen, Archäologisches Institut
- Greifswald: Universität Greifswald, Akademisches Münzkabinett
- Greifswald: Universität Greifswald, Theologische Fakultät
- Halle: Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg, Archäologisches Museum
- Heidelberg: Ruprecht-Karls-Universität Heidelberg, Heidelberg Zentrum Kulturelles Erbe
- Jena: Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena, Archäologisches Museum
- Jena: Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena, Orientalisches Münzkabinett
- Kiel: Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel, Antikensammlung Kunsthalle zu Kiel
- Kiel: Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel, Institut für Klassische Altertumskunde, Alte Geschichte
- Leipzig: Universität Leipzig, Alte Geschichte
- Leipzig: Universität Leipzig, Universitätsbibliothek
- Mannheim: Universität Mannheim, Historisches Institut
- Marburg: Philipps-Universität Marburg, Archäologisches Seminar
- Mainz: Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz, Historisches Seminar
- Münster: Universität Münster, Institut für Klassische Archäologie und Christliche Archäologie/Archäologisches Museum
- Passau: Universität Passau, Alte Geschichte
- Regensburg: Universität Regensburg, Klassische Archäologie
- Rostock: Universität Rostock, Heinrich-Schliemann-Institut für Altertumswissenschaften
- Stuttgart: Universität Stuttgart, Historisches Institut
- Trier: Universität Trier, Alte Geschichte
- Tübingen: Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen, Forschungsstelle für Islamische Numismatik Tübingen
- Tübingen: Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen, Klassische Archäologie
- Wuppertal: Bergische Universität Wuppertal, Biblisch-Archäologisches Institut
- Würzburg: Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg, Münzkabinett/Martin von Wagner-Museum

Italy

- Milan: Collezione numismatica, Università Cattolica di Milano

Netherlands

Leiden: Papyrologisch Instituut, Universiteit Leiden

Nijmegen: Radboud Institute for Culture & History, Radboud University

Switzerland

Fribourg: Musée BIBLE+ORIENT, Université de Fribourg

Ukraine

Lviv: Кафедра археології та історії стародавніх цивілізацій,
Львівський національний університет імені Івана Франка
(Department of Archaeology and Ancient Civilizations History,
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